

Spring and Gravity Laws of Vibration Energy Harvesting: Duality of Mass and Anomalously Nonmonotonic Nonlinear Power

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Usual theory has it that large power is only attained by using large mass in harvesting of vibration energy. But can a heavy harvester be displaced at all or meaningfully under small vibration sources? Large mass means large materials with high costs, less ease of transportation and high difficulty of integration into portable technologies. Herein, it is derived and proved that power is inversely proportional to mass, and directly proportional to the stiffness of spring and to the gravity of the local environment where vibration energy is harvested. Systematic studies of several commercial and proof-of-concept piezoelectric, magnetic and mechanical vibration energy harvesters supported and established these mathematical findings. This paper further clarified the theory of maximizing power by mass increment and revealed that it only holds provided the displacement amplitude of vibration source is sufficient, otherwise power regresses to inverse of mass. Nonmonotonic nonlinear power which is common in reality is in accordance with expectations of dual mass and power relationships of both inverse and direct proportionalities, mediated by differing structural arrangements and properties of spring, fluctuation or permanence of displacement amplitude of vibration source, and characteristic scavenging of surface gravitational power.

I. INTRODUCTION

By the last century, there were already interests in devices that can produce their own electrical power based on energy harvested from movements around them. Reports of flashlights from Dynamos in early 20th Century highlighted these primal interests [1–4]. Vibration is movement, whether periodic or aperiodic, whether of disturbed or of undisturbed equilibrium origin. Hence, vibration energy harvesting encompass energy collected from all kinds of movements including from electromagnetic, electrostatic, electrical, thermal, mechanical, chemical and sound sources [5–9], even various noises from structures of spacecrafts [10] and vibrations of earth due to waterfalls, microseism and ocean infragravity waves [11, 12]. Given the fact that everything moves, vibration energy is an alternative energy source to alleviate the shortcomings of existing energy sources. Solar and wind energy harvesting have proved to be insufficient and erratic in many environments, e.g. underwater, surface, sub-orbital, orbital and deep space.

A harvester designed to capture or absorb energy from vibrations usually amplifies that energy through resonance and then converts it into a usable electrical energy through a transduction process. Such a harvesting device is typically composed of a mass, m , and a spring, K , which together bring about the resonance, either as the harvester's own natural frequency $f_n = 1/2\pi\sqrt{K/m}$ Fig. 1 or from coupling to the natural frequency of the vibration source. There are exceptions to this norm, which are non-resonant vibration energy harvesting devices designed and built without resonance [13–16].

FIG. 1. Simple schematic model of a vibration energy harvester showing mass, spring and damper.

One key problem for vibration energy technology is the limitation of power to merely how big the mass of a harvester is [5–7, 17–19]. This has imposed undue design difficulties for achieving high-performance harvesters. And because this was believed to be associated with linear devices only [5–7, 17], nonlinear mechanics were proposed and attempted to address this problem [20–27]. These proposed approaches have been supposed to be also limited by mass of an energy harvester [19, 28], leading to the conclusion that the basic limits on energy that can be harvested by nonlinear vibration energy harvesters are yet to be completely understood [28, 29].

In these dialogues, gravitational parameters relating to local gravity environments were overlooked in spite of the: known implications of gravity on surface of earth [12], revelations in horizontal vibration experiments [30] and development of a spectroscopy technique for measuring gravitational resonance due to impact at very low scales [31]. Hence, whether a vibration energy harvester is on high mountain, valley or underwater, at one earth location or another, whether it is on surface of a comet

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in space [32], orbiting a body [33] or freely travelling, would make a difference to the amount of power that it can produce. Apparently, the importance of differences in gravity environments have been highlighted by NASA through the development of Active Response Gravity Offload System (ARGOS) and the Glenn Zero-G facility to mimic a reduced gravity, microgravity or near-zero gravity (near weightlessness) environment on Earth [34, 35].

It remains an issue that major focus of reported works on spring stiffness is using it for just designing of frequency at which resonance occurs in vibration energy harvesters [5–7, 17, 36]. Spring which comes as mechanical, visible and physical to touch also comes in invisible and non-physical forms such as electromagnetic, electrostatic, magnetic, acoustic, thermal, gravitational, electronic, chemical or their hybrids. In practice, all these types of spring can deliver more power without need to increase mass, which is beneficial to overall reduction in weight and size. For some vibration energy harvesters, an independent spring designed with known stiffness is combined with an independent mass, like mechanical spring in a pendulum, gravitational spring holding Comet 67P, etc. But for others like in a piece of piezoelectric cantilever beam, a harvester is simply an object with inherently knotted stiffness and mass such that a change in intrinsic mass of the harvester is synonymous to an automated change in intrinsic stiffness, and vice-versa.

The neglect in ascertaining state of displacement amplitude of vibration energy sources is an additional drawback to the discussions about how mass pegs the limits of power. State of displacement amplitude is often assumed to be always constant but in reality it could fluctuate. This fluctuation does matter to amount of power harvested or delivered by a harvester. A sinusoidal sweeping excitation using a laboratory shaker causes displacement amplitude of the shaker plate (upon which the harvester is mounted) to fluctuate across the sweeping frequencies. The shaker plate is usually assumed to be steady. Overlook of the actual status of displacement amplitude of vibration source leads to presumption that using larger mass for harvesting always achieves larger power.

All these above-mentioned drawbacks in the debate on limitation of power to largeness of mass of a vibration energy harvester are addressed in this paper with theories and experimental validations. Based on uncomplicated analytical mathematical solutions, theoretical concepts in Section II sheds light into the theory of large mass large power, then establishes theory of small mass large power, and finally solved for a theory that establishes proportionality of power to gravity. Real-life experiments and data that validated the theories are presented in Section III. Product data of different commercial vibration energy harvesters by independent manufacturers and experimental results of proof-of-concept devices were all used for the validations. Finally, conclusion in Section IV was drawn based on validated theories and experimental findings from the energy harvesters.

II. THEORETICAL CONCEPTS: MATHEMATICAL MODELLING (ANALYTICAL)

A. First Theory: Large Mass Large power (Harvester Design by Mass) - Classical Review [5–7, 17–19, 28, 29]

This theory is characterized by the need to have big device mass in order to achieve large power generation. It is further characterized by low harvesting frequency, high materials cost, large payload, and near-zero or zero displacement of a large mass by a low-amplitude vibration source. The theory was first introduced from mathematical analyses of a base-excited single degree-of-freedom device (i.e. can only move from its base in one direction, Fig. 1) using general mass-spring-damper model, $m\ddot{y} + c\dot{y} + ky = -m\ddot{x}_0$, where relative displacement $y = x - x_0$, k represents stiffness, c is for damping constant, x stands for displacement of moving mass m , while x_0 represents the base displacement [17].

From assuming that the vibration source is an infinite source of power, i.e. that the movement of the device does not affect the vibration source and that the mass of this vibration source is considerably greater than the moving mass, the theory concluded that the net electrical power in response to the base motion, taken as sinusoidal in form, is given as

$$\frac{m\zeta_e X_0^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_n}\right)^3 \omega^3}{\left[1 - \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_n}\right)^2\right]^2 + \left[2\zeta_e \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_n}\right)\right]^2} \quad (1)$$

where X_0 is the displacement amplitude of vibration source, ζ_e is the transducer damping ratio, ω is the frequency of sinusoidal vibration input and ω_n is the natural frequency (resonant angular frequency) of the harvester. Accordingly, damping is important for a harvester's performance and a low damping ratio would lead to increased power generation, in particular for applications where the vibration frequencies are centred at around one point (narrow band). But for applications where the vibration frequencies are diverse and spread (broadband), a higher damping factor is more important so that the response bandwidth of the harvester is widened enough to catch the diverse vibration frequencies. It was indicated that more power is produced at higher frequencies of vibration compared to lower frequencies because the amount of power generated is proportional to the cube of the vibration frequency.

If a harvester set in motion at base by a sinusoidal vibration source is operated at resonance, that is, $\frac{\omega}{\omega_n} = 1$, the amount of power that can be extracted out from such harvesting device $P_{extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$ is inversely proportional to transducer damping ratio,

$$\frac{mX_0^2\omega_n^3}{4\zeta_e} \quad (2)$$

and if the transducer damping ratio is zero, then an infinite amount of power is produced. However, this was concluded as highly impractical as the maximum amount of power produced and that can be extracted at resonance $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$ cannot be infinite

$$m\zeta_e D_{max}^2 \omega_n^3 \quad (3)$$

where D_{max} is the maximum distance that the internal moving mass in the device can travel. This maximum distance is determined and limited by the mere size and shape of any harvester, and if ζ_e is too small, the displacement of the internal moving mass may be so large that it exceeds D_{max} . Therefore ζ_e has to be high enough to prevent this. But undesirable internal damping ζ_i such as mechanical joint friction, air resistance and magnetic damping must be taken into account. Hence, ζ_e must have ζ_i added to it so that the total damping ζ_T becomes $\zeta_e + \zeta_i$. This would then result in the amount of power that can be extracted at resonance $P_{extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{m\zeta_e X_0^2 \omega_n^3}{4(\zeta_e + \zeta_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

and currently serves for real-world practicability as it accounts for all forms of damping. As substantial amount of internal damping will reduce the electrical power output at resonance, ζ_i was suggested to be at least at an order of magnitude lower than ζ_e for a good harvester design that produces power at single frequency from a narrow band vibration source. Even though there is still need to minimise internal damping ζ_i , the amount of power that can be extracted has to be optimized to yield a maximum power by adjusting ζ_e to equal ζ_i , giving the maximum amount of power that can be extracted out of an energy harvester $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{mX_0^2 \omega_n^3}{16\zeta_e} \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{mX_0^2 \omega_n^3}{16\zeta_i} \quad (5b)$$

As such ζ_e in Eq. (5a) or ζ_i in Eq. (5b) can be used to account for damping.

From all these, rules were formulated for designing a vibration energy harvester on the basis of direct proportionality of mass with power, and state that the: (a) mass should be as large as possible within the available volume of a harvester, and (b) extent which the mass can move should be as large as possible in the space available [17]. Now, these rules are derived and written herein in a mathematical form for sinusoidal vibration source, having accounted for damping, yielding maximum power that can be extracted at resonance $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{mD_{max} X_0 \omega_n^3}{4} \quad (6)$$

where m is the internal moving mass, D_{max} is the maximum possible displacement of the internal moving mass within a harvester, ω_n is the natural frequency (resonant angular frequency) of the harvester, and $X_0 = [X_0 + \Delta X_0]$ is the displacement amplitude of vibration source with fluctuating state equivalent to $\Delta X_0 > 0$.

For the last decades, it was concluded that for a given vibration input of sinusoidal form, an upper bound power (some of which are lost and cannot be extracted) for a device of any architecture, construction, transduction mechanism, or operating mode can be normalized to $P \leq mY^2\omega^3$ where Y is the displacement [7], split into the input displacement X_0 of the vibration source and maximum possible displacement of the internal moving mass D_{max} within a harvester. From [5], this upper bound power taken as the total dissipated power within the damper is at resonance $P_{diss. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{mX_0^2 \omega_n^3}{4\zeta_T} \quad (7)$$

and following the rules advocated by [17] this equation is now further derived to

$$\frac{mD_{max} X_0 \omega_n^3}{2} \quad (8)$$

Eqs. (6) and (8) offer advantages over earlier solutions [5–7, 17] because they can easily be used when comparing performances of different vibration energy harvesters as it is uncommon for companies and researchers to provide complete data, such as internal and transducer damping ratios. Also, D_{max} can be replaced by a measured D to give actual power value in real time if X_0 is known.

Another well-known vibration source signal is random white noise, which has broad range of frequencies and suitable for broadband harvesters [5–7, 17–20, 28, 37, 38]. Closed form solution of random white noise for resonating linear devices gives maximum power that can be extracted as $P_{max. extract. random (white) noise} \leq m \frac{S_a}{2}$ where m is the internal moving mass and S_a is the power spectral density of the white noise base acceleration [18, 20]. This maximum power limit was evoked for nonlinear devices but total mass instead of internal moving mass was used in the solution and proposed to be valid regardless of the type of nonlinearity in a harvester [19]. Interestingly and very importantly, the power spectral density S_a of white noise base acceleration (broadband) has a unit of m^2/s^3 , which is same unit for $Y^2\omega^3$ of the sinusoidal base acceleration (single frequency or narrow-band driven vibrations). This means that the maximum power that can be extracted from any harvester set into motion by a sinusoidal or a white noise vibration source is governed similarly.

The maximum power that can be extracted from an energy harvesting device set on base motion by a white noise vibration source assumes that all dissipated energy is extracted but this is a condition that gives infinite power in the case of single frequency sinusoidal form,

which was considered impracticable. In the real world, there is always some sort of damping as discussed earlier. Therefore, for real-world applications, damping parameter in the response of any harvester to white noise base acceleration (broadband) must be accounted for, and the famous Miles equation in vibration analysis [39] becomes handy and applicable to give dissipated power under random (white) noise source $P_{diss., random (white) noise}$

$$\frac{m\pi f_n a_{rms}^2}{4\zeta_T f^2} \quad (9a)$$

$$\frac{m\pi f_n S_a}{4\zeta_T f} \quad (9b)$$

where a_{rms} is acceleration of the vibration source (base acceleration), f_n is the natural frequency of the harvester, f is the frequency at which the base acceleration power spectral density (S_a) is flat, and ζ_T is the total damping equivalent to ζ_e (transducer damping ratio) + ζ_i (internal damping).

At resonance, where $f_n = f$, this gives the dissipated (available) power $P_{diss. resonance, random (white) noise}$

$$\frac{m\pi S_a}{4\zeta_T} \quad (10)$$

while the amount of power that can be extracted gives $P_{extract. resonance, random (white) noise}$

$$\frac{m\pi\zeta_e S_a}{4\zeta_T^2} \quad (11)$$

leading again to the condition of optimization where $\zeta_e = \zeta_i$ such that the amount of power extracted is maximized to give $P_{max. extract. resonance, random (white) noise}$

$$\frac{m\pi S_a}{16\zeta_e} \quad (12)$$

Obviously and evidently, there is similarity at resonance between power generated from random white noise and sinusoidal vibration sources. Hence, solution of one form applies to the other. The difference appears to be only by a theoretical factor of $8\pi^2$, due to the frequency in radians (angular frequency) for the sinusoidal waveform.

B. Second Theory: Small Mass Large Power (Harvester Design by Spring)

Clearly, the overemphasis on the theory of large mass large power has been consequential to the notion that upper bound power performance of new harvesters would remain limited to just their weights and sizes [5–7, 17–19], with multiple masses taken as the only way to achieve multiple natural frequencies [40]. Theory of mass does not provide a designer of vibration energy harvester with insights on how to tailor power with physical and non-physical springs. Hence, new expressions for power that

use spring stiffness instead of mass are derived here to provide an alternative guide for designers and builders. This spring theory is characterized by small device mass equating to large power, high harvesting frequency (easily convertible to low frequency or DC with electronics; high frequency = high energy), low materials cost, small payload, and large displacement of small mass by a vibration source with small amplitude.

The general expression of dissipated power under sinusoidal vibration source $P_{diss., sinusoidal}$ is

$$\frac{1}{2}c[\omega Y]^2 \quad (13)$$

which is derived from $P_{diss.} = c \int_0^v v dv$ for a non-constant velocity $v = \omega Y$ and force $F = cv$ where c represents the damping constant, ω means angular frequency and Y signifies the relative displacement of mass when a harvester is set into motion from its base. The general form of Y is

$$\frac{m\omega^2 X_0}{[(K - m\omega^2)^2 + (c\omega)^2]^{0.5}} \quad (14)$$

where K is the spring stiffness, m is the internal moving or total mass and X_0 is the amplitude of base vibration source. Substituting the expression for Y in $\frac{1}{2}c[\omega Y]^2$ yields dissipated power $P_{diss., sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{m^2\omega^4 X_0^2}{2c} \quad (15)$$

and at resonance where $\omega = \omega_n$ gives dissipated power $P_{diss. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{m^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{m}}\right)^4 X_0^2}{2c} \quad (16a)$$

$$\frac{m^2 \left(\frac{K}{m}\right)^2 X_0^2}{2c} \quad (16b)$$

yielding the final solution

$$\frac{K^2 X_0^2}{2c} \quad (17)$$

Since the damping constant is $c = 2m\omega_n\zeta_T$, where ζ_T is the total damping ratio, the final solution Eq. (17) is then rewritten to become

$$\frac{K^2 X_0^2}{4m\omega_n\zeta_T} \quad (18)$$

giving the amount of power that can be extracted at resonance $P_{extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{\zeta_e K^2 X_0^2}{4m\omega_n\zeta_T^2} \quad (19)$$

and so that maximized when $\zeta_e = \zeta_i$, gives an amount of power $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{K^2 X_0^2}{16\zeta_e m \omega_n} \quad (20)$$

Eqs. (18), (19) and (20) can also be derived such that power ‘resolves’ independently of mass and damping ratio, with distance and velocity travelled by the internal moving mass in the harvester. This is useful in circumstances where some parameters are available and some are not. The amount of power dissipated within the damper is thus derived $P_{diss. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{K D_0 X_0 \omega_n}{2} \quad (21a)$$

$$\frac{K v_m X_0}{2} \quad (21b)$$

yielding the amount of power that can be extracted $P_{extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\zeta_e K D_0^2 \omega_n \quad (22a)$$

$$\zeta_e K D_0 v_m \quad (22b)$$

and the maximum amount of power that can be extracted when $\zeta_e = \zeta_i$ $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$

$$\frac{K X_0^2 \omega_n}{16\zeta_e} \quad (23a)$$

$$\frac{K D_0 X_0 \omega_n}{4} \quad (23b)$$

$$\frac{K v_m X_0}{4} \quad (23c)$$

The spring theory states explicitly that power produced at resonance, whether the dissipated power or the power that can be extracted normally or maximally, is directly proportional to the spring stiffness and the displacement amplitude of the vibration source, but inversely proportional to the mass and natural frequency of the mass-spring unit of a vibration energy harvesting device. Spring theory clearly contradicts the direct proportionality of power to mass in the first theory [5–7, 17–19]. Consequently, the smaller the mass, the higher the power at any given spring stiffness, and the stiffer the spring, the higher the power at any given mass. The upper bound power is a design question to be answered by the designer [41–43], which will in part be defined by whether the spring is designed linear or nonlinear [20] and also by the choice of inherent nature of that spring, that is whether it is mechanical, magnetic, gravitational, electrostatic, chemical and others. The issue of higher resonance frequency due to higher spring stiffness is nowadays less critical as frequency conversions to convenient standard forms for electrical power delivery are possible with modern electronic hardware.

C. Third Theory: Large or Small Mass Large Power (Harvester Design by Gravity)

A question in vibration energy harvesting is whether a change of gravity in an environment will affect the power performance of a harvester. For instance, can an energy harvester designed at 9.8 m/s^2 on surface of earth have same performance when in a different level of gravity environment like the mountains, underground, space, moon, etc.? This question cannot be addressed by mere speculation but by representing gravity parameter in the solutions of power. This is done herein by replacing X_0 with g/ω_n^2 and then substituting in Eqs. (6) and (20) to produce a maximum amount of power that can be extracted at resonance in a gravity environment, $P_{max. extract. resonance, sinusoidal}$,

$$\frac{m D_{max} \omega_n g}{4} \quad (24a)$$

$$\frac{K^2 g^2}{16\zeta_e m \omega_n^5} \quad (24b)$$

$$\frac{K^2 X_0 g}{16\zeta_e m \omega_n^3} \quad (24c)$$

As seen from the equations, gravity theory is characterized by either small (Eqs. (24b) and (24c)) or large mass (Eq. (24a)) to yield large power. The route to take is a choice that must be decided by a designer, taking into account the gravity level of the environment for deployment, material costs, payload requirements and displacement amplitude of vibration source. Based on the natural relationship of mass with gravity, deriving and solving analytically from gravitational potential energy of any given vibration energy harvester with a mass m moving a maximum height or distance of D_{max} with a frequency ω_n under a surface value of the acceleration of gravity, g , the available surface gravitational power $P_{G_{surface}}$, be it of earth or of any other space objects, can be written

$$mg D_{max} \omega_n \quad (25)$$

Only a fraction of this power seems to be deployed in opposing the force of gravity in vibration energy harvesters. At constant parameters under same conditions, the total power dissipated and extracted normally or maximally at resonance is numerically equal for theories of mass, spring and gravity BUT not equal to the surface gravitational power which is produced in tandem by mass. For example, Eqs. (24a), (24b) and (24c) yield equal numeric results as Eqs. (6) and (20), but nonequivalent result to Eq. (25) with a large residual gravity power of $3/4 \times mg D_{max} \omega_n$ when solved for Eq. (24a). Harvesting and transducing of this residual gravity power is a design, fabrication and positioning issue but also depends on whether displacement amplitude of vibration source X_0 is static or fluctuating. In general, when the X_0 is fluctuating, the internal displacement of mass D_0 or D_{max} may or may not fluctuate depending on design.

In a micro-g or zero-g environment, the force of gravity is reduced or absent. And as a result, vibration power will be transferred from the source of vibration to a harvester with only tiny or zero opposition from the force of gravity. However, damping due to frictions, air drag, natural resistance of materials to flow of charges, etc are still present. Consequently, damping will be experienced by mass m travelling a distance D in a harvester. Therefore, the solutions for mass and spring theories, for example in Eqs. (6) and (20), can be applied in zero gravity environment, and is very important to design the maximum distance D_{max} travelled by mass to be as large as possible within a specified harvester size.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATIONS (EXPERIMENTS, DATA TREATMENTS AND REAL-LIFE APPLICATIONS)

As found from the mathematical models in previous section, increasing mass of a vibration energy harvester may or may not lead to increase in power. In this section, real-life cases are demonstrated based on actual experiments (Fig. 2) and independently reported tests and data [44–46]. Different kinds of energy harvesters were studied and their results are presented: Midé Technology Corporation in Fig. (3) and Table. (I), Brüel & Kjaer in Fig. (4) and Vibraticity, Inc in Fig. (5). In the experiments, microelectromechanical (MEMS) piezoelectric accelerometer precalibrated at factory was used as shown in the set-up in Fig. 2. It serves dual purpose as a transducer and as an accelerometer. To check and confirm for reliability, the piezoelectric accelerometer was recalibrated using laser vibrometer. Recalibration with the laser follows that a laser beam from a vibrometer was focused onto the piezoelectric transducer as it was affixed on top of energy harvester. This was the approach for calibration of the transfer functions, which was based on the relationship between velocity and voltage. Also, this recalibration was performed to take account of capacitance of cables used for the measurements, particularly those cables that were not manufactured or supplied by the same factory. Recalibrated values were not expected to deviate from factory-calibrated values because a charge-to-voltage converter (typically also called a charge preamplifier) was used in this case instead of a voltage preamplifier. Normally, values calibrated at factory stage do change due to differences in capacitance if cables are different from factory specified cables when voltage preamplifiers are used.

Charge-to-voltage converter transforms charge from piezo transducer to voltage, where any gain is controlled by using internal feedback capacitance across an operational amplifier. The output voltage of the charge-to-voltage converter is equal to the charge at input, that is this output voltage is not influenced by the input capacitance because in the ideal case all charge flows from the accelerometer or energy harvester to the input. This

FIG. 2. The set-up for vibration energy harvesting measurements including digital vibration measurements using random noise inputs, calibration using a combination of laser vibrometer and random-noise base excitation, and the entire electronics for the signal input and output

charge flow Q is directly proportional to the current $I = \frac{dQ}{dt}$ but this current at the input flows only from the piezos and feedback capacitor, respectively, and is equivalent at both. The relationship between this current and output voltage V is given as $I = C \frac{dV}{dt}$ since $Q = CV$. An ideal amplifier has zero input current, consequently current is defined in terms of charge produced by the piezoelectric transducers so that the output voltage is actually $V_{output} = \frac{Q_{piezo}}{C_{feedback}}$. This output voltage is supposed to be open-circuit but it is dropped across low impedance ($< 10\Omega + 47\mu F$) at the output of the charge-to-voltage converter.

Fundamentally, only reactive power is at the input (zero power dissipated measured in units of Volt-Amps-Reactive) whereas there is real power component at the output (actual power dissipated measured in units of Watts). Therefore, with the charge-to-voltage converter used in these measurements, apparent power composed

FIG. 3. Real-life results of V20W, V25W, V21BL, V21B, V22BL, V22B piezoelectric vibration energy harvesters manufactured by Midé Technology Corporation for maximum power outputs at 0.25 and 1.00 g-accelerations ($1 g = 9.8 m/s^2$) when various extra masses were added [44, 45]. Plots of performances are represented by: *square* symbol for vibration source at 1g-acceleration without extra mass; *cross* symbol for vibration source at 1g-acceleration with with 1 gram extra mass (data unreported for V20W and V25W); *circle* symbol for vibration source at 1g-acceleration with 2.4 grams extra mass for V20W, V25W, V21BL and V21B but 2.0 grams extra mass for V22BL and V22B; *star* symbol for vibration source at 0.25g-acceleration with 2.4 grams extra mass for V20W, V25W, V21BL and V21B but 2.0 grams extra mass for V22BL and V22B; *right - pointed - triangle* symbol for vibration source at 0.25g-acceleration with with 7.8 grams extra mass (data unreported for V21BL, V21B, V22BL and V22B); *left - pointed - triangle* symbol for vibration source at 0.25g-acceleration with with 15.6 grams extra mass (data unreported for V21BL, V21B, V22BL and V22B). *Asterisks on 2.4 grams in the legend denotes that 2.4 grams extra mass was only loaded for V20W, V25W, V21BL and V21B but 2.0 grams extra mass was loaded for V22BL and V22B.

of both real and reactive components (in units of Volt-Amps) were measured. This arrangement is considered optimum for transporting harvested energy to the electrical domain when piezoelectric transduction is used for energy harvesting.

A. Midé Technology Corporation [44, 45]

V20W, V25W, V21B, V21BL, V22B and V22BL are piezoelectric vibration energy harvesters produced by Midé Technology Corporation. By design and nature, they are basically cantilever beams made of piezoelectric materials upon which an extra mass can be added

to increase power output. A cantilever beam is a beam fixed at one end such that the other end which is free can deflect when caused to move. Based on their manufacturer's specification datasheet [45], volumes, mass ratios and RMS tip displacements were derived and together with their maximum power outputs are presented in Table (I). A combination of layered materials such as FR4, Epoxy, Piezo, and Espanex was used to make the harvesters [44] and as such their total densities can be approximated as equal.

The intrinsic mass of V20W is practically the largest of all the six vibration energy harvesters because of its largest volume. It was therefore anticipated that V20W must 'consistently' produce more power than all

TABLE I. Monotonic and Nonmonotonic Nonlinear Power: Maximum amounts of power at different levels of acceleration of vibration source and at different amounts of extra mass added to six different piezoelectric vibration energy harvesters that were manufactured by Midé Technology Corporation Ref. [45]

	Volume ^a x10 ⁻⁶ (m ³)	Mass ^b ratio	D_{RMS} ^c x10 ⁻³ (m)	P_{max} ^d 1g, 0gram (mW)	P_{max} ^e 1g, 1gram (mW)	P_{max} ^f 1.0g, 2.4grams (mW)	P_{max} ^g 0.25g, 2.4grams (mW)	Remarks
V20W	1.880	1.000	0.898	1.719	-	2.692	0.272	largest mass
V25W	1.327	0.706	1.347	1.468	-	2.431	0.134	
V21BL	0.878	0.467	1.616	0.262	0.513	1.484	0.157	largest D_{RMS}
V21B	0.597	0.317	0.539	0.250	0.658	1.311	0.114	
V22BL	0.328	0.174	1.078	0.210	1.050	1.840 ^h	0.280 ^h	
V22B	0.194	0.103	0.269	0.050	0.260	0.590 ⁱ	0.070 ⁱ	smallest mass

^a Harvester volume derived from dimensions of harvesters, and without the connector volume which has a constant value for all the six harvesters. See Ref. [45]

^b Mass ratio = harvester volume divided by largest harvester volume. $Mass = density \times volume$. At \sim uniform material density Ref. [44], $mass \sim volume$.

^c D_{RMS} is root mean square value of tip-to-tip displacements of the piezoelectric cantilever beam harvesters.

^d Maximum Power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source for no added mass (zero grams), as in Ref. [45]. This is a monotonic nonlinear power spectrum.

^e Maximum Power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source for added mass of 1 $gram$, and unavailable for V20W and V25W, as in Ref. [45]. This is a nonmonotonic nonlinear power spectrum.

^f Maximum Power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source for added mass of 2.0 $grams$ (V22B and V22BL) to 2.4 $grams$, as in Ref. [45]. This is a nonmonotonic nonlinear power spectrum.

^g Maximum Power P_{max} at 0.25 g -acceleration or $\sim 2.45m/s^2$ of vibration source for added mass of 2.0 $grams$ (V22B and V22BL) to 2.4 $grams$, as in Ref. 45. This is nonmonotonic nonlinear power spectrum.

^h Added mass of 2.0 $grams$ as in Ref. [45]

ⁱ Added mass of 2.0 $grams$ as in Ref. [45]

the rest of harvesters in accordance with the theory of large mass large power [5–7, 17–19]. But reported data showed the contrary as demonstrated in Fig. (3) and Table. (I), which present results for various mass additions to tips of the cantilever piezoelectric harvesters when vibration source has accelerations of 0.25 g and 1 g (1 $g = 9.8 m/s^2$). These real-life results depict that maximum power outputs of: (a) each energy harvester increased steadily as extra mass was added to the tip (monotonic nonlinear power) at same g -acceleration of vibration source; and (b) different energy harvesters remarkably demonstrated anomalous increases and decreases when extra masses were added to their tips at same and at different g -accelerations of vibration source (nonmonotonic nonlinear power).

That is, power outputs of V20W were not consistently the highest, and also other harvesters with more original mass than others performed worse in their power outputs sometimes. However, when the energy harvesters or power generators were with only their original intrinsic masses, that is with no extra mass added to the tips of the cantilever beams (zero grams), V20W generated the most maximum power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source. This conformed to the theory of large mass large power, demonstrating a monotonic nonlinear power spectrum, with power increasing nonlinearly as masses of the harvesters increased.

But when 1 $gram$ of additional mass was added to the tips of the harvesters (except for V20W and V25W with unreported data), the maximum amount of power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source failed to conform

to the theory of large mass large power and yielded an anomalous behaviour where V22BL > V21B > V21BL > V22B. This is a nonmonotonic nonlinear power, where both increases and decreases in power occur with addition of mass.

When 2.0 $grams$ (V22B and V22BL) to 2.4 $grams$ (V20W, V25W, V21B and V21BL) of additional masses were added to the tips of the harvesters, the maximum amount of power P_{max} at 1 g -acceleration of vibration source failed again to conform to the theory of large mass large power and yielded an anomalous behaviour where V20W > V25W > V22BL > V21BL > V21B > V22B. Interestingly, V22BL produced the third largest amount of power at this 1.0 g -acceleration of vibration source, noting that only 2.0 $grams$ extra mass was added to its tip, an amount lower than 2.4 $grams$. This further confirms anomalous nonmonotonic nonlinear power.

But what happened when the vibration source was lowered from 1.0 g -acceleration to 0.25 g -acceleration ($\sim 2.45 m/s^2$)? Fig. (3) and Table. (I) demonstrate that the maximum power failed again to conform to the theory of large mass large power and produced even a more intense anomalous nonmonotonic nonlinear power spectrum, where V22BL > V20W > V21BL > V25W > V21B > V22B. Under this 0.25 g -acceleration of vibration source, V22BL produced the largest amount of power of all the six harvesters, noting that V20W has an intrinsic mass ratio or volume that is six times more than that of V22BL and not forgetting that only 2.0 $grams$ extra mass was added to its tip in contrast to 2.4 $grams$ added to V20W. Now, taking a look when the

FIG. 4. Real-life results of power performance of Brüel & Kjaer LDS electromagnetic shaking device [46] used as a vibration energy harvester that follow the one degree-of-freedom model in Fig. (1). Plots are represented by: *square* symbol for shaker plate without extra mass and *circle* symbol for shaker plate with extra mass of 0.1 *kg*.

extra masses were increased to 7.8 grams and 15.6 grams at same 0.25 *g*-acceleration, noting that results for the other harvesters were unreported, it is clear that V20W generated less power than V25W which has less original intrinsic mass.

Obviously real-life results of six commercial vibration energy harvesters are not consistent with the theory that power increases with addition mass. The theory of spring stiffness (eq. (20)) predicts that a smaller mass can outperform a larger mass. From the relationship of spring stiffness and length, $K = 3EI/L^3$ where E = Young's modulus, I = area moment of inertia and L = beam length, it appears that the smallest length of 1.00 inch for the V22BL piezo beam laminated at a balanced position of the centre of cantilever beam is responsible in part for its anomalous performance. The lengths for V21BL and V21B are 1.40 inches while V20W and V25W are 1.81 inches [45]. Also, the extra masses added to the tips of the harvesters changed the interactions of these harvesters with the opposing force of gravity and also with the available gravitational power as in eq. (25).

B. Brüel & Kjaer [46]

LDS V406-V408 are electromagnetic shaking devices produced by Brüel & Kjaer (Fig. (2)) and can be found in most laboratories across the world where they are used for vibration testing and structural analyses. They are fundamentally harvesters with mass, spring and damper illustrated in Fig. (1). According to the manufacturer's specification data [46], they have a moving plate of effective mass = 0.2 *kg* suspended on a spring of axial stiffness

= 12300 *N/m*, and have continuous RMS displacement of $6.22 \times 10^{-3}m$.

To measure the electrical power output produced by vibrations of LDS V406-408, a miniature-sized piezoelectric transducer or Endevco Model 2222C as described earlier was attached to the surface of 0.2 *kg* shaker plate. Known voltage (1 *V*) and current (1 *A*) signals of sinusoidal or random noise were supplied to the shaker for vibration. Power output was obtained by measuring the voltage and current outputs from the transducer using either a multimeter, industrial grade portable oscilloscope (scopemeter) or a data-logging and analyses computer with MATLAB software for signal processing via a charge to voltage converter. Frequency response was obtained using Fast Fourier Transform algorithm which took the Discrete Fourier Transform of both input and output data. Transfer function was then obtained by dividing the output spectrum by the input spectrum using the MATLAB environment. After adding more mass of 0.1 *kg* to the shaker plate, the procedures were repeated.

With mass and spring stiffness specified by Brüel & Kjaer for LDS V406-V408, they would have a theoretical natural frequency, $f_n = 1/2\pi\sqrt{K/m}$, at approximately 39.5 *Hz*, which was found to be in agreement with measured real-world value (Fig. (4)). By adding an extra mass of *ca.* 0.1 *kg*, the real-world resonance shifted down to *ca.* 29 *Hz* in line with theoretical expectation. Using a random white noise vibration source for continuous or steady-state displacement amplitude within range of 200 μm , the 0.2 *kg* shaker plate was found to produce more power than when the mass was increased to 0.3 *kg*. As the spring stiffness and the displacement amplitude of the vibration source (shaker) remained unchanged, the vari-

FIG. 5. Top: Schematic showing three different magnetomechanical vibration energy harvester DMDS, DMSS and SMSS, where DMDS means Double Magnets Double Mechanical Springs, DMSS means Double Magnets Single Mechanical Spring and SMSS means Single Magnet Single Mechanical Spring. Bottom: Real-life experimental results of power performances of three different magnetomechanical piezoelectric vibration energy harvesters DMDS, DMSS and SMSS.

ation of mass with power followed the herein proposed theory of spring stiffness where addition of mass leads to decrease in power, as in $0.2\text{ kg} > 0.3\text{ kg}$ instead of the expected norm $0.3\text{ kg} > 0.2\text{ kg}$. This result attests again to the reality that power does not always increase with increasing mass which was taken as an absolute rule by the classical theory of larger mass larger power.

C. Vibratricity, Inc. [47, 48]

The vibration energy harvester in this case was a proof-of-concept magnetomechanical piezoelectric harvesters, with over 20 unique configurations: that is, having many

different forms of structural arrangements and characteristics such that each configuration can act as an independent energy harvester for a unique characteristic type of response to vibration energy sources or for generating a unique amount of electrical power [47, 48]. Three of these configurations as shown in Fig. (5) were deployed for the experiments, each as an independent energy harvester. They were placed under state of non-fluctuating (constant) displacement amplitude of random white noise vibration source (*approx.* 150 μm).

These three vibration energy harvesters include: (a) DMDS: has two identical magnets of equal values of mass. Each magnet was attached separately to two suspended mechanical springs that are copies of each other in struc-

ture. But both separate magnets are linked together by a magnetic spring formed between them. DMDS has a natural frequency of 284 Hz , a total internal moving mass of 0.022 kg , a spring stiffness of 70051 N/m , and a total damping ratio ζ_T of 0.042. (b) DMSS: has two identical magnets of equal values of mass. Both magnets were attached together to one suspended mechanical spring. DMSS has a natural frequency of 138 Hz , a total internal moving mass of 0.022 kg , spring stiffness of 16540 N/m and total damping ratio ζ_T of 0.067. (c) SMSS: has one magnetic mass attached to one suspended mechanical spring. This harvester has a natural frequency of 194 Hz , an internal moving mass of 0.011 kg , a spring stiffness of 16343 N/m , and a total damping ratio ζ_T of 0.036. All parameter values were obtained from real-time measurements.

DMDS, DMSS and SMSS were mounted successively on Brüel & Kjaer LDS V406-408 shaker, which acted as a vibration source. Each harvester was operated at six percent of its total operational capacity. Their power outputs were measured using same instrumentation for LDS V406-408 measurements for consistency (Fig. (2)). When instrumentation was replaced with resistor, the electrical power measurements were repeated successively. Random noise and sinusoidal signal were supplied as form of the vibration source input to the shaker. Voltage and current outputs from Endevco Model 2222C attached to the surface of the vibrating shaker plate were measured to determine the actual power input by the vibration source in setting the harvesters into motion from their bases. Displacement, velocity and acceleration measurements were also taken using Polytec desktop scanning Laser vibrometer (Class 2). Transfer functions were obtained by dividing the output spectrum of each harvester by the output spectrum of the vibration source.

DMDS and DMSS have the same real-life mass of 0.022 kg but the results (Fig. (5)) demonstrate that DMDS produced more power than DMSS. The major reason is that DMDS has higher spring stiffness, four times stiffer than DMSS. It is a validation that power increases as spring stiffness is increased when the vibration source displacement amplitude is constant, that is, a condition under which lesser mass or stiffer spring brings about higher power. SMSS has the least mass, which is half the mass of DMDS. Also, SMSS has spring stiffness that is a quarter the spring stiffness of DMDS. The lesser mass of SMSS counteracted its softer spring and as a consequence, SMSS produced power lower than DMDS. On the other hand, SMSS has almost the equivalent stiffness but half the mass of DMSS. Power produced by SMSS is higher than the power generated by DMSS, and this sharply contrasts with the results of DMDS, which has same mass as DMSS.

If one follows the theory of large mass large power [5–7, 17–19], without recourse to spring stiffness, gravity interplays, and state of vibration source displacement

amplitude, then power produced by these three configurations in the real-world would have been: DMDS = DMSS > SMSS. Instead, the evidence of power produced by these three vibration energy harvesters in real-life followed: DMDS > SMSS > DMSS, which is a nonmonotonic nonlinear power relationship with mass.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results provide direct evidences for the inverse proportionality of mass to power, and further brought to bare the dual nature of mass as been both inversely and directly proportional to power. All these simply mean that the expectation of power to always increase with mass is unfounded. Adding mass to increase power without proportionate increment in displacement amplitude of vibration source causes a downward turn in power. Sufficiency of displacement amplitude of vibration source to move mass and by how far the mass moves define linear or monotonic nonlinear increase of power with mass. Whether displacement amplitude of vibration source is fluctuating or constant contributes to the dual nature of mass in forming nonmonotonic nonlinear power.

Power is directly proportional to spring stiffness and gravity. There fore, focusing on spring stiffness and on gravity in the design and fabrication of vibration energy harvesters offers alternative paths to achieve high performance without enlargement of mass. There are different natures of spring to choose from, including the invisible types like magnetic spring. The structural arrangements of mass and spring within the size limits of a harvester can make significant difference in amount of harvested power, and scavenging of its surface gravitational power.

Beside multi-alternative paths to design, high performance, reduced volume sizes, reduced weights, cost reductions and scavenging access to more power sources, this work also provides tools and approaches for: gravity experiments [30, 31, 34, 35], mobile applications [49], vibration harmonics of plasma sensing technology [50], vibration-induced densest packing of self-assembled spherical and non-spherical particles [51] and phonon stiffening in quartic and general oscillators [52].

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